

MORPHOLOGY OF LOWER LIMB MUSCLES IN MECHANICAL INJURY OF LOWER LIMB

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Summary: The study included 48 adult rats with mechanical injuries of the lower limb, divided into two groups. The first group (24 rats) received local anesthesia, the second group (24 rats) - general anesthesia. In all patients, biopsies were taken from the muscles of the lower limb for histological analysis 24 and 72 hours after injury. The following morphometric parameters were assessed: muscle fiber edema, inflammatory infiltration, degenerative changes and muscle tissue regeneration.

Keywords: morphometry, edema, degenerative changes, muscle tissue regeneration.

Research aim. The aim of the study was to compare morphometric changes in lower limb muscles after mechanical injury in rats receiving local and general anesthesia.

Materials and methods. The experiment was conducted on 48 sexually mature rats, 5-6 months old (m=200-220 g). The animals were kept in standard conditions that meet sanitary regulations. Special marks on the body were used to identify the rats. During the experiment, the animals were healthy, with no changes in behavior. The rats in the experiment were anesthetized by intraperitoneal administration of bupivacaine (150 mg/kg). In two groups, on the 1st and 3rd days after, the muscles of the lower limb were taken during autopsy in compliance with the principles of humane treatment of animals, some of the animals were removed from the experiment by euthanasia, under chloroform anesthesia, by puncture of the left ventricle until complete exsanguination. The obtained biomaterial (muscle tissue) was fixed in 10% formalin solution. After fixation, the muscle tissue was excised and embedded in paraffin using the standard technique. Next, sections 5-7 μm thick were made and stained with hematoxylin and eosin.

Results and discussion. These data allow a visual comparison of the degree of muscle tissue damage and the inflammatory response depending on the type of anesthesia in the two groups over time. Average area of necrotic fibers (mm^2): reflects the degree of muscle tissue damage. In the general anesthesia group, there is a larger area of necrotic fibers, which indicates more serious damage. The second indicator indicates the intensity of the inflammatory response. In the general anesthesia group, the percentage of inflammatory cells is higher, which indicates a more active inflammatory reaction. The next indicator is the state of the blood supply to the muscle tissue. In the local anesthesia group, the density of the vascular network is higher, which may indicate better blood supply. The last morphometric parameter measures the volume of edema in the muscle tissue. In the general anesthesia group, the level of edema is higher, which indicates more pronounced tissue damage. Based on the data obtained, the results were entered in tables No. -1 and 2.

Таблица №1. Morphometric data 24 hours after injury

Parameter	Group I (local anesthesia)	Group II (general anesthesia) Group II I (local anesthesia)
Average area of necrotic fibers (mm ²)	0,15 ± 0,02	0,30 ± 0,05
Percentage of inflammatory cells (%)	20 ± 3	35 ± 5
Vascular density (vessels/mm ²)	8 ± 1	6 ± 1
Edema level (mm ³)	1,2 ± 0,2	2,5 ± 0,3

Таблица №2. Morphometric data 72 hours after injury

Parameter	Group I (local anesthesia)	Group II (general anesthesia)
Средняя площадь некротизированных волокон (мм ²)	0,10 ± 0,01	0,25 ± 0,04
Percentage of inflammatory cells (%)	15 ± 2	30 ± 4
Vascular density (vessels/mm ²)	10 ± 1	7 ± 1
Edema level (mm ³)	0,8 ± 0,1	2,0 ± 0,2

CONCLUSION. Thus, the analysis of these indicators allows us to conclude that general anesthesia leads to more serious damage to muscle tissue and a more pronounced inflammatory reaction than local anesthesia.

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